

The value of using open persistent identifiers in research - ORCID

(**PARSEC**: Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Re-use through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas)

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About Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

Persistent Identifiers (*PIDs*)

Well-established persistent identifiers (PIDs) provide a trusted basis for open science.

A PID has a set of associated metadata that is machine-readable and must be structured in a URL (Dappert *et al.*, 2017).

Persistence is related to the service offered by the PID system and not to the identifier itself. This means that there is an organisation committed to keeping the identifier resolvable. The identifier leads users to the services that guarantee the reference (Kunze, 2013).

- A more open science
- A more interconnected science
- Need of **interconnected** and **interoperable** PIDs

Joint proposal

- Non-for profit
- Always free for researchers and contributors
- Open infrastructure
- Identification and persistence
- Community governed
- Sustainable
- Global

The logo for DataCite, featuring a stylized blue and black circular icon above the word "DataCite" in a blue and black sans-serif font. Below the name is the tagline "FIND, ACCESS, AND REUSE DATA" in a smaller, black, all-caps font.

Research outputs have a life-cycle, which includes data movement

PIDs can make research FAIR

Data should be Findable	<p>F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (DOI)</p> <p>F2. data are described with rich metadata</p> <p>F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes</p> <p>F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource</p>
Data should be Accessible	<p>A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol</p> <p>A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable</p> <p>A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary</p> <p>A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available</p>
Data should be Interoperable	<p>I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles</p> <p>I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data</p>
Data should be Reusable	<p>R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</p> <p>R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license</p>

Open Science

Open Science Taxonomy

About Data and Metadata

On the importance of DOIs for data and metadata

The problem

- Papers only tell a small fraction of the story, hard to comprehensively evaluate a research study based on paper alone
- Complex experimental protocols and data may aggravate the reproducibility problem
- Open and FAIR research increase reproducibility and reuse, infrastructure and tools are available but adoption is fragmented

The solutions

- A DOI makes research outputs uniquely identifiable, and discoverable
- DOIs and metadata help FAIR research

Why is it so important to cite data?

- support proper attribution and credit
- support collaboration and reuse of data
- enable reproducibility of findings
- foster faster and more efficient research progress, and
- provide the means to share data with future researchers

Data Citation Examples

We recognise that the challenges associated with data publication vary across disciplines, and we encourage research communities to develop citation systems that work well for them. Our recommended format for data citation is as follows:

Creator (PublicationYear). Title. Publisher. Identifier

It may also be desirable to include information about two optional properties, Version and ResourceType (as appropriate). If so, the recommended form is as follows:

Creator (PublicationYear). Title. Version. Publisher. ResourceType. Identifier

DataCite Commons

Type to search...

Works People Organizations Repositories

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2926-8353>

Shelley Stall

Shelley Stall is the Vice President for the American Geophysical Union's D. organizations, and the broader research community to improve data and how research data is managed and valued. Better data management resu program and project manager, software architect, database architect, per and data integration architect for international communities, both nonpr guide development of practical and sustainable data policies and practic community.

Links

[AGU Blog and Resources - Data Leadership](#)
[AGU Data Leadership Program](#)

Other Profiles

[ORCID](#)
[Impactstory](#)
[Europe PMC](#)

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2926-8353>

A researcher that has openly published research datasets can now find out many times these published datasets have been viewed, downloaded, and cited by visiting their DataCite Researcher Profile page.

Accessibility Achievements

92% of the researcher's associated DOIs have metadata with rights as CC-BY, CC0 or public domain license.

295 Works

Filter Works

Type to search... x Q

Publication Year

<input type="checkbox"/> 2022	73
<input type="checkbox"/> 2021	145
<input type="checkbox"/> 2020	45
<input type="checkbox"/> 2019	30

Publication Year

Work Type

License

How is metadata used?

How good is your metadata?

How can I improve my metadata?

Identifiers are necessary, but are not enough:

- Deposit reference metadata (enable OJS references Linking plug or equivalent);
- Add funding information (enable OJS plugin);
- ROR iDs with affiliation metadata;
- Allow and encourage authors to share their ORCID iD using the ORCID API (authenticated iDs), and to enable auto-update;
- Check your [participation report](#)

Better research through better metadata

A rich and reusable open network of relationships connecting research organizations, people, things, and actions; a scholarly record that the global community can build on forever, for the benefit of society.

About ORCID

What is ORCID?

- Born in 2012 (100% virtual)
- Non-for profit, non commercial
- Open code and API
- Global vision and scope
- Guided by researcher privacy and control principles
- Supported by members
- 2019 breakeven - sustainability

Open
Researcher and
Contributor
Identifier

10th
Anniversary

ORCID Global

+1.2K Members

78% Research Orgs (Universities)

7% Publishers

4% Associations

3% Funders

3% Government

55 countries

73% consortium

Records

15M

Active Records

+9M

Consortium

25

Active systems
integrated

4.3K

Users giving permission to
systems for record update

6.3M

Legend

 National ORCID Consortium

 ORCID member

Created with mapchart.net

ORCID Services

 Persistent Identifier
(PID): ORCID iD

 Record connected
to your ORCID iD

 APIs

- 1) Researchers **create** their ORCID ID
- 2) **Populate** and **connect** their record to databases and systems

Stored information ready to share and not have to input the same information in several systems

The API connects and synchronise data between systems

Interoperability

INTEGRATIONS WITH ORCID API

ORCID

- Free identifier for people
- Hub between systems with information validated by the source

Institutional ORCID integrations

DSpace

DATA180
SMART SOLUTIONS FOR ACADEME

FACULTY180

ejprints
repository software

altum
ProposalCentral

bepress™

Clarivate
Analytics

DigitalMeasures
Strategic tools for higher education

SYMPLECTIC
Elements

smartsimple

slandora

ExLibris
Esploro

DataCite
FIND, ACCESS, AND REUSE DATA

FACT Science

<https://info.orcid.org/es/orcid-enabled-systems/>

<https://info.orcid.org/certified-service-providers/orcid-certified-service-providers-list/>

Integrate with systems

- Provides an authenticated ORCID iD
- Gives permission to read/write on the ORCID record
- The organisation becomes a trusted organisation

Visibility

Users can change visibility settings

PUBLIC

Everyone can see

LIMITED

Trusted organisations to which you previously gave permission

PRIVATE

Only the user can see

ORCID iD

iD
[https://orcid.org/
0000-0001-5727-2427](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5727-2427)

Is this you? [Sign in to start editing](#) Printable version

Published name
Sofia Maria Hernandez Garcia

Name
Sofia Garcia

Also known as
S. M. Garcia, Sofia Maria Garcia

Biography
Sofia Maria Hernandez Garcia is used for testing and demonstrating ORCID records.

Activities Expand all

- > **Employment (2)** Sort
- > **Education and qualifications (4)** Sort
- > **Invited positions and distinctions (3)** Sort
- > **Membership and service (2)** Sort
- > **Funding (1)** Sort
- > **Research resources (2)** Sort
- > **Works (6)** Sort
- > **Peer review (2)** Sort

Emails >
s.garcia@orcid.org

Websites & social links >
Faculty profile webpage

Other IDs >
Profile system identifier: A-123456
ResearcherID: L-8716-2018
eScientist: 0000-0001-5727-2427

Countries >
United States

AUTO-UPDATE FOR WORKS

AUTO-UPDATE IN ACTION

▼ Works (33)

ORCID Annual Report 2016.pdf
Figshare
2017 | other
DOI: 10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.4810213
Source: DataCite

Open Access in Context: Connecting Author Workflows Using ORCID Identifiers
Publications
2016-09-26 | journal-article
DOI: 10.3390/publications4040030
Source: Crossref

Jake VanderPlas @jakevdp · 2h
My first @JOSS_TheOJ paper passed review and is published! joss.theoj.org/papers/10.2110...

Jake VanderPlas @jakevdp
Wow... that was fast! @ORCID_Org @JOSS_TheOJ

ORCID

Hi Jacob VanderPlas,
You have 1 new notification in your ORCID inbox - see summary below.
see more details.

▼ Works (1)

mt_clustering: Clustering via Euclidean Minimum Spanning Trees [http://dx.doi.org/10.21105/joss.00012](https://dx.doi.org/10.21105/joss.00012)
more info... Add now

View details in your ORCID inbox

Sara Hänzi @SaraHaenzi

have not yet heard from @J_Exp_Biol about proofs but @ORCID_Org tells me @CrossrefOrg wants to add the new article to my ORCID - cool!

5:13 pm - 4 Nov 2016 <https://twitter.com/SaraHaenzi/status/794467574557904896>

Why authenticated ORCID iDs?

ORCID is all about correctly identifying who's who, so it's important that you get the correct iD for each person. No room for typos here! By collecting authenticated iDs - where each user logs into their ORCID account before their details are added to your collection - you can be sure you're connecting the right person with the right iD. [Learn more about authenticated iDs](#)

SHARE MY ORCID ID

A simple way to collect authenticated ORCID iDs

Create your iD collection

Three simple steps to collecting authenticated ORCID iDs!

Want to collect authenticated ORCID iDs from a group of researchers? Attendees at your next event, perhaps? Everyone in your research group/lab? Or others? Share My iD makes it as simple as 1, 2, 3!

1. [Create a new iD collection](#) (all you need is your own ORCID iD!)
2. Use the Share link to request iDs by email or on a webpage.
3. Visit the Share link to view and download the iDs you've collected.

Not sure if everyone already has an ORCID iD? No problem! New users can register for an iD and add it to your collection at the same time.

<https://share-my-id.orcid.org/P6a5M8dL>

ORCID in Policies and Guidelines

Many governments and funders are adopting ORCID as part of their national research strategies

*By way of this Notice, NIH, AHRQ, and CDC announce that individuals supported by research training, fellowship, research education, and career development awards **will be required to have ORCID iDs** (Open Researcher and Contributor Identifiers) beginning in FY 2020.*

National Institutes of Health (NIH): Requirement for ORCID iDs for Individuals Supported by Research Training, Fellowship, Research Education, and Career Development Awards Beginning in FY 2020, <https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-19-109.html>

*"It is proposed that Australia's research sector **broadly embrace the use of ORCID** as a common researcher identifier."*

Joint Statement of Principle: ORCID - connecting researchers and research, A proposal to adopt ORCID as a common researcher identifier across the Australian university research sector. - Australian National Data Service (ANDS). http://ands.org.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0007/417346/orcid-joint-statement-of-principle.pdf

*"...common unique PIDs for research management information ... are strongly encouraged; **ORCID, the researcher identifier must be supported to identify all authors and contributors.**"*

UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Open Access Policy, 2021 <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/UKRI-060821-UKRIOpenAccessPolicy-FINAL.pdf>

*"In this sense, **SENACYT adopts ORCID as a persistent international unique identifier for researchers**, technologists and innovators at the national level to create a favorable ecosystem with the aim of increasing national and international collaboration, increasing the visibility of the country and timely managing the knowledge generated in Panama."*

The National Secretariat of Science, Technology and Innovation of the Republic of Panama, October 2020 <https://www.senacyt.gob.pa/la-senacyt-se-convierte-en-miembro-de-la-organizacion-orcid/>

*"Where possible, contributors should be uniquely identifiable, and data uniquely attributable, through identifiers which are persistent, non-proprietary, open, and interoperable (e.g., through **leveraging existing and sustainable initiatives such as ORCID** for contributor identifiers....)"*

European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation, (2017) Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

3 NEXT GENERATION METRICS FOR OPEN SCIENCE

3.2 Targeted Recommendations

3.2.3 Developing research infrastructures for open science

RECOMMENDATION #8: The European research system and Open Science Cloud should adopt ORCID as its preferred system of unique identifiers, and an ORCID iD should be mandatory for all applicants and participants in FP9. Unique identifiers for individuals and research works will gradually improve the robustness of metrics and reduce administrative burden. ORCID provides researchers with a unique ID and associates this ID with a regularly updated list of publications. It is already backed by a growing number of funders across Europe (<http://about.orcid.org/>). The EC and ERC should utilise ORCID IDs for grant applications, management and reporting platforms, and the benefits of ORCID need to be better communicated to researchers and other stakeholders (Galsworthy & McKee, 2013).

Where possible, contributors should also be uniquely identifiable, and data uniquely attributable, through **identifiers** which are persistent, non-proprietary, open and interoperable (e.g. through leveraging existing sustainable initiatives such as [ORCID](#) for contributor identifiers and [DataCite](#) for data identifiers).

European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2017). *Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020*. Disponible en: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

Strongly recommended additional criteria for all publication venues:

- > Support for PIDs for authors (e.g., ORCID), funders, funding programmes and grants, institutions, and other relevant entities.

Coalition S, Plan S principles and implementation (Parte III: Guía y Requisitos Técnicos) <https://www.coalition-s.org/addendum-to-the-coalition-s-guidance-on-the-implementation-of-plan-s/principles-and-implementation/>

UKRI OA policy – response from UK ORCID consortium lead

Posted: August 24, 2021 Updated: August 24, 2021 | [News Policy](#) | [PIDS UKRI](#)

As the lead organisation for the UK ORCID Consortium, we are delighted to see what is pragmatically a mandate for ORCID iD, for all contributors to a scholarly output in the new [UKRI Open Access Policy](#)

Technical requirements for journals and publishing platforms (4g) and institutional and subject repositories (5d):

common unique PIDs for research management information (for example identifiers for funders and /or organisations) are strongly encouraged; ORCID, the researcher identifier, must be supported to identify all authors and contributors

To see that mandate, and further PID recommendations, applied to both repositories and publisher workflows will result in a great improvement to the information underpinning the scholarly ecosystem. The [Jisc response to the whole policy](#) states:

...we will continue to work with institutions and stakeholders to build capacity, adoption and implementation of persistent identifiers...

UKRI announces new Open Access Policy

6 August 2021

UK Research and Innovation's (UKRI) new policy will increase opportunity for the findings of publicly funded research to be accessed, shared and reused.

Following extensive consultation with the sector, UKRI has published a single Open Access Policy for research publications that acknowledge funding from its councils.

UKRI's updated policy requires immediate open access for peer-reviewed research articles submitted for publication from 1 April 2022.

Monograph requirement

It also includes a new requirement for monographs, book chapters and edited collections published from 1 January 2024 to be made open access within 12 months of publication.

UKRI will provide increased funding of up to £46.7 million per annum to support the implementation of the policy.

UKRI Chief Executive, Professor Dame Ottoline Leyser, said:

“ The new UKRI Open Access Policy is an important step towards realising our vision of a more open and transparent research culture, which is widely shared across the research and innovation community.

Digital Persistent Identifiers

Background: Section 4(b)(v) of NSPM-33 directs that “*Consistent with applicable Federal laws and statutory authorities, within 1 year of the date of this memorandum, funding agencies shall establish policies regarding requirements for individual researchers supported by or working on any Federal research grant to be registered with a service that provides a digital persistent identifier for that individual.*” Section 4(b)(vi) directs, in part, that “*agencies should standardize forms for initial disclosures as well as annual updates, integrating digital persistent identifiers wherever appropriate and practicable....*”

Objective: Describe how research agencies will incorporate digital persistent identifiers (DPIs)—also known as Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)—into disclosure processes to bolster research security and integrity while reducing administrative burden.

Implementation Guidance

Research agencies should work to implement DPIs into their electronic systems and processes as quickly as is feasible with appropriate protections for personally identifiable information. Until that time, completion of required disclosures using previous systems and processes may still be required. When available, the DPI option will facilitate population of this information into the requisite format.

1. Incorporation of DPIs into grant and cooperative agreement⁹ application and disclosure processes

EXECUTIVE OFFICE OF THE PRESIDENT
OFFICE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY POLICY
WASHINGTON, D.C. 20502

August 25, 2022

MEMORANDUM FOR THE HEADS OF EXECUTIVE DEPARTMENTS AND AGENCIES

FROM: Dr. Alondra Nelson
Deputy Assistant to the President and Deputy Director for Science and Society
Performing the Duties of Director
Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP)

SUBJECT: Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research

This memorandum provides policy guidance to federal agencies with research and development expenditures on updating their public access policies. In accordance with this memorandum, OSTP recommends that federal agencies, to the extent consistent with applicable law:

1. Update their public access policies as soon as possible, and no later than December 31st, 2025, to make publications and their supporting data resulting from federally funded research publicly accessible without an embargo on their free and public release;
2. Establish transparent procedures that ensure scientific and research integrity is maintained in public access policies; and,
3. Coordinate with OSTP to ensure equitable delivery of federally funded research results and data.

Federal agencies should take actions to ensure that these elements of scientific and research integrity are in place in order to strengthen public trust in federally funded science.

To achieve these goals, the following steps should be taken by federal agencies, as appropriate and consistent with their missions. By December 31st, 2024, federal agencies should submit to OSTP and OMB a second update to their public access plans specifying approaches taken to implement the provisions in this Section 4. Agencies should complete and publish full policy development for plans implementing these provisions by December 31st, 2026, with an effective date no later than one year after the publication of the agency plan. Federal agencies should, consistent with applicable law:

- a) Collect and make publicly available appropriate metadata¹⁵ associated with scholarly publications and data resulting from federally funded research, to the extent possible at the time of deposit in a public access repository. Such metadata should include at minimum:
 - i) all author and co-author names, affiliations, and sources of funding, referencing digital persistent identifiers,¹⁶ as appropriate;
 - ii) the date of publication; and,
 - iii) a unique digital persistent identifier for the research output;
- b) Instruct federally funded researchers to obtain a digital persistent identifier that meets the common/core standards of a digital persistent identifier service defined in the NSPM-33 Implementation Guidance,¹⁷ include it in published research outputs when available, and provide federal agencies with the metadata associated with all published research outputs they produce, consistent with the law, privacy, and security considerations.
- c) Assign unique digital persistent identifiers¹⁸ to all scientific research and development awards¹⁹ and intramural research protocols that have appropriate metadata linking the funding agency and their awardees through their digital persistent identifiers.

Having a persistent identifier improves your digital presence

THE ASTROPHYSICAL JOURNAL LETTERS

OPEN ACCESS

First M87 Event Horizon Telescope Results. I. The Shadow of the Supermassive Black Hole

The Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration, Kazunori Akiyama^{1,2,3,4}

- Increase citation to your work
- Connects you with collaborators around the world, in all disciplines
- Improves Open Science practices

ORCID is a community effort

ALWAYS:

- **Populate** your ORCID record
- **Use** your ORCID iD whenever possible
- Encourage your organization to integrate systems with the ORCID API so information can be added to your record

<https://pidforum.org/>

Know are
share more
about PIDs

ROR Chat Room	30
A chat room for the Research Organization Registry (ROR) Community	
RDA PID IG	2
This category is for anything related to the PID IG, an active Interest Group of the Research Data Alliance focused on Persistent Identifiers.	
PIDs canal en español	14
Canal para comentar y compartir información sobre PIDs (identificadores persistentes) en español.	
PIDs-Kanal auf Deutsch	10
Dieser Kanal dient der Kommentierung und dem Austausch von Informationen über PIDs (persistente Identifikatoren) auf Deutsch.	
PID Forum Champions	1
This is a private channel for PID Forum Champions and Experts.	
PID Services	4
Post anything related to PID Services here.	